

A student perspective on the blended learning experience in a project based context - A case of the blended learning experience, and how it affected students ability to manage, collaborate, and communicate in an international cross-disciplinary project

Johannes Kruse Hellmers¹, Robert Nedergaard Nielsen¹

¹Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

Email: jhellm14@student.aau.dk, rnni17@student.aau.dk

Abstract

Based on an expectation from the authors on the beneficial learning outcome from joining the Erasmus+ project Improving Employability Through Internationalization And Collaboration, namely that this would strengthen their intercultural competence, improve their ability to take part in agile collaboration and strengthen their project management skill, they signed up for the project. This paper will present a case-based study of the authors experience, and the knowledge gained on top of the study curriculum, of joining such a project. It will shortly describe the project, analyse areas in which the authors gained significant extra-curricular skills, and describe outcomes of the process. This will result in the authors suggesting advice to future teachers and students embarking on similar learning experiences, that they make need to find projects with interesting and relevant problems as these heighten motivation and challenges both the technical and interpersonal skills of the students involved. The conclusion based on these is that a blended learning experience such as is described, will have significant benefits to the intercultural competence of students, as long as this is made explicit as an outcome in the beginning. It will also conclude that the main challenge to cross-disciplinary work lies in communication.

Keywords: Blended learning, international collaboration, student experiences.

1 Introduction

In this submission, the goal of the authors is, to better understand the experiences with a blended learning experience through careful examination of the problems that arose in the given multinational and interdisciplinary nature of the project.

The initial goal of joining an international project, where to gain more experience in work across both borders and disciplines. This goal was reinforced by the multiple pleasant experiences of working with projects in problem based learning at Aalborg University, and was seen by the Danish student as a way to further challenge the abilities not challenged by ordinary lectures and textbook exercises.

In the following, a description of the project setup, an evaluation of the project's challenges and results, a discussion about these and a conclusion on the findings are done.

By understanding the case of this project's context, the authors hope to bring a more personal view of such experiences to educators. This means also that the generality of this experience is not going to be in focus for the submission, mainly because of the constrained formal knowledge in the field of educational research.

2 Project setup

The project itself is part of the Erasmus+ project Improving Employability Through Internationalization And Collaboration (EPIC)(Pedersen, Kirkova, Kuladinithi, & Janssen, 2019) and is a collaboration between three parties. Four Danish network engineering students, a Turkish software student and six Brazilian production engineering students.

As the EPIC project spans a large variety of students from different universities and with different progress, the amount of ECTS points vary for each person. As such this is important to note, when evaluating such an experience, in the case of this project, the points were distributed as seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of course load of the participants.

Country	ECTS pr. person
Denmark	20
Brazil	2
Turkey	8

The stated goal of the project was to use the competencies of the three groups to create a system that could improve the waste collection in Brazil's capital, Brasilia.

2.1 Process

The collaboration was initiated with a kick-off seminar in Hamburg. This was a week long seminar that gave insights in to different subjects, amongst them were an intercultural workshop, giving a brief introduction to Hofstede's cultural dimensions, and how these can be applied when managing an intercultural process (Figure 1), a talk about taking up a large scale Sustainable Development Goal(SDG) challenge as students and social activities.

Figure 1: Hofstede's cultural dimensions (2017).

2.2 Communication

During the seminar, the group also defined how to communicate during the virtual collaboration phase. As the EPIC team had already created a Slack channel for the students and supervisors it was chosen to continue using Slack for written communication. As a part of this discussion it was also decided that the group should have video meetings during the collaboration phase, here it was chosen to use Google hangouts as it is accessible to everyone through a browser. These communication agreements can be summarized as:

- A weekly update on the joint Slack, explaining what has been done during the week and potential problems.
- Online meetings every 14 days, where results and problems can be discussed in order to find a solution together.

2.2.1 Assessment

As a part of the EPIC project the group were also asked to create some criteria to assess the other members' contribution to the project. The idea was then to run an assessment three times during the collaboration after the kick-off seminar in Hamburg, in the middle of the collaboration and towards the end.

The group decided on the criteria:

- Good meeting structure and meeting feedback.
 - Definition: To establish good meeting structure, all teams are supposed to answer the following questions after every meeting:
 - Did we get expected information from the other teams during the meeting.
 - Are we following the schedule and are we satisfied with the results so far?
 - How efficient was meeting timewise.
- Correct use of agreed online tools.
 - Definition: The Team members should use the slack channel and respond to messages at least once a week.
- Cultural Awareness
 - Definition: Students act respectfully during the meeting and understand each other's point of view.
 - Did I have any communication challenges within the team during the meeting.
 - Was I able to express myself efficiently?
 - Are we being considerate about cultural differences?

These assessments should then be used in the following meeting in order to evaluate whether or not the members lived up the expectations from the other group members.

2.3 Content

This seminar was also used for generating an initial concept for a system that could help mitigate some of the problems. The initial concept the group came up with can be seen on Figure 2. The concept consists of a number of sensors placed in the waste containers, a network system that can facilitate the communication from the sensors to a centralized server.

The server will then store the measurements from the sensors and process it into a format that could be used in a route optimization algorithm and for creating a dashboard giving the company an overview of the status of their containers.

Figure 2: Illustration of the initial concept created by the group.

This initial concept was then divided up into subsystems with a goal of making each group of students to work in their field of study. The Danish network engineering students would make the sensors, the network system for sending the measurements and a server that could provide the data from the measurements to the others. As a part of the division process the interfaces between the subsystems were defined, and a prioritisation of tasks were devised, so progress could be made more effective. This division can be seen on Table 2.

Table 2: Deliverables of the groups.

Team	Deliverables
Network engineers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensor system, capable of measuring waste level. • Network system for sending measurements to a centralized server.
Production engineers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating communication to the waste management company. • Dashboard for displaying sensor data.
Software engineer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Route optimization.

3 Evaluation and results

During the first weeks of the virtual collaboration phase, it was experienced what can happen when working in an intercultural project, as the group had forgotten to take local holidays into account. This resulted in next to no communication and process on the project during this first period. Upon experiencing this the preparation done in Hamburg became incredibly relevant, as this had given the students a more positive approach to tackling the challenge of cultural differences and brought a more adaptive mindset.

As the load from the universities was much higher during the beginning of the semester the weekly updates disappeared as the three parties did not feel that they had made enough progress to make meaningful updates, and the 14 days meeting schedule were found to be a suitable time frame for updating each other. During the final development phase, it could have been useful to utilize the weekly meetings, as the larger steps in development led to misunderstandings in what progress was made.

Looking at the total project period meetings every fortnight worked quite well giving people a chance to inform themselves on the progress of the goals and tasks stated at kick-off. Having the meeting as a video call resulted in fewer misunderstandings compared to only communicating with sound as interpretations and gestures were helping breach the gap of the language barrier that exists between the students. The video also helped with making the project group feel more socially connected, than an audio or text format would have.

The Danish group decided that everyone should participate in the meetings giving everyone an idea of what is going on and to make sure the right message came across and were understood correctly.

The project was also drastically affected by the COVID-19, as the lockdown limited the Danish students' access to parts needed in order to develop the hardware used in the final system.

The lockdown also inhibited the teams in each country to meet physically. This impacted the overall flow of information and made smaller frustrations into more heavy discussion.

International travel restrictions have also made an impact on the timeframe, as the systems cannot be fully implemented and tested on location until such restrictions are lifted.

4 Discussion

During the project, the authors have experienced different challenges both by working in an international, cross-disciplinary project and a project created based on the goals of the study curriculum. However, these are the challenges that will actually teach them how to work in an intercultural and cross-disciplinary context. The challenges started during the kick-off seminar in Hamburg in the process of finding a solution to the problem satisfying the requirements for accreditation by the universities involved, were solved by each subgroup of the project. This means that the all the students at least managed to break even on investing time and effort in an international project.

The Danish students' collaboration with the production engineering students from Brazil made an even bigger impact, by forcing them to evaluate the way that they as network engineering students communicate a proposed solution and the progress in developing this solution. This process of communicating the chosen technology and its working helped them realize how much of the communication was dependent on the recipients having the same technical understanding as them. This made it clear that the true understanding of the underlying subject was not as clear and originally thought. Upon realising that the language barrier and different backgrounds they were forced to reformulate explanations during meetings. The need to explain how the Danish students were solving challenges to an audience without their own technical language seems to have a beneficial impact on learning outcomes (Cohen, Kulik, & Kulik,1982).

5 Conclusion

The most valuable lesson that the authors have drawn from the experience of doing a project in an international and multidisciplinary setting, is to value the importance of regular communication. Such communications must be culturally aware, and otherwise empathic towards the receiver in order to be successful. The communication must aim to clarify a framework of clear requirements for interfaces, when the project is split into teams sitting each in their part of the world.

The idea to bring people to the same location at the projects beginning there becomes a foundation of possible success, as such a meeting can give the students the tools to communicate effectively. In the authors opinion the project would have been impacted to a severe degree if this had been foregone.

Another important takeaway for the authors, upon making the project, is that embarking on interdisciplinary learning experiences enhances more than just the ability to collaborate, but that this also helps to deepen the extent of the theoretical knowledge for students.

The project also helped underscore again that working in the setting of problem-based learning, especially in collaboration with an outside partner, helps the motivation of students, as commitments to deliver are a natural part of the process.

6 References

- Cohen, P. A., Kulik, J. A., & Kulik, C.-L. C. (1982). Educational Outcomes of Tutoring: A Meta-analysis of Findings. *American Educational Research Journal*, 19(2), 237–248
- Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions. (2017, June 17). B2U - Business-to-You.Com. <https://www.business-to-you.com/hofstedes-cultural-dimensions/>
- Pedersen, J. M., Kirkova, M., Kuladinithi, K., & Janssen, N. V. H. (2019). EPIC: Making Multinational Student Projects Happen. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE)*, 9, 219-228.